

A NOTE ON THE SAPONIN FROM *SAPINDUS LAURIFOLIUS*, VAHL

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Two species of soapnut tree, namely *Sapindus mukorossi*, Gaerten and *Sapindus laurifolius*, Vahl, are indigenous to India. Saponin ($C_{17}H_{26}O_{10}$) has been isolated by Weil (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1901, 289, 363) from *S. mukorossi*. The sapogenin occurring in *S. mukorossi* and in *Sapindus saponaria*, Linn. has been proved to be identical with hederagenin (Jacobs, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1925, 63, 621; 64, 379). The preparation of crude saponin (in an yield of 17.21%) from soapnuts derived from *S. mukorossi* has been described by Sarin and Beri (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1939, 31, 712).

In the present paper, a method for the isoation of pure saponin from *S. laurifolius* has been described. The method differs in some respects from the one followed by Sarin and Beri (*loc. cit.*).

The pure saponin melted at 145° and on hydrolysis it furnished a sapogenin, m. p. 328-29°. Acetate of the sapogenin was found to melt at 170°. The sapogenin is believed to be identical with hederagenin (m. p. 327-29°; diacetate, m. p. 170-75°, recorded by Jacobs, *loc. cit.*).

Isolation of Saponin.—The pericarp which constituted 46% of the soapnut (*S. laurifolius*) was dried in steam in vacuum and powdered. The powder (100 g.) was exhausted with ethyl acetate (500 c.c.) in a soxhlet. The solvent in the extract was then distilled off and the residue dissolved in water, boiled with animal charcoal and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness in a steam-bath. The powdered residue was dissolved in the minimum quantity of absolute alcohol and the solution poured into dry ether with stirring. The flocculent precipitate was removed, redissolved in boiling distilled water, charcoaled and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated in a steam-bath and finally dried in a steam-bath under reduced pressure. A white substance, m. p. 145°, was thus obtained (14.5 g.). The saponin is insoluble in ether, chloroform, benzene and petroleum ether but is soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohol, water and warm pyridine. It is acidic and dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid. The orange sulphuric acid solution turns violet after some time. (Found : C, 56.20; H, 7.74 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the Saponin : Isolation of Hederagenin.—The saponin was hydrolysed with dilute methyl alcohol (1:1) containing 5% hydrochloric acid in the usual way. The resulting sticky mass was separated and washed with petroleum ether which removed an oil having terpene-like odour. The insoluble solid substance on crystallisation from methyl alcohol formed rhombic crystals melting at 328-29° (after sintering at 323-24°). The sapogenin is insoluble in ether, water, benzene and petroleum ether. It is sparingly soluble in cold alcohol but readily soluble in pyridine and dilute alkali. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid to a colourless solution which becomes deep red after sometime. [Found : C, 76.39; H, 10.10. $C_{21}H_{30}O_4$ (hederagenin) requires C, 76.48; H, 10.36 per cent].

The *diacetate*, prepared in the usual way, formed colourless needles, m. p. 170°. [Found: C, 73.51; H, 9.19. $C_{18}H_{24}O_6$ (hederagenin diacetate) requires C, 73.63; H 9.54 per cent].

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